

HOW DID DIFFERENT FOREST MANAGEMENT OPTIONS AFFECT WOODY ASSORTMENTS?

Negar Rezaie¹, Ettore D'Andrea², Luigi Pari¹, Giorgio Matteucci²

¹ Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA), Research Centre for Engineering and Agro-Food Processing, Via della Pascolare, 16 - 00015 Monterotondo Scalo, Italy

² National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Institute for Agriculture and Forest systems in the Mediterranean (ISAFoM), Via Patacca, 85, 80056 Ercolano NA, Italy

ABSTRACT: Forests and wood-based products, from sustainably managed forests, contribute to climate change mitigation. Forests and their products are therefore one of the most effective and completely natural systems for the sequestration and storage of carbon. Improved silviculture will often increase the net carbon sequestration in forests and produce high quality wood assortments. In this context we evaluate different silvicultural options in producing wood assortments in three beech forests where different silvicultural treatments were performed. Our results suggested that innovative silvicultural treatments, even though in each site the percentage of removed biomass is similar between the two thesis, produce higher the quantity of round and fuel wood than traditional ones.

Keywords: *Fagus sylvatica*, woody assortments, sustainable forest management, climate change mitigation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Forests and wood-based products, derived from sustainably managed forests, removing annually 569 million tons of CO₂ per year [1], contribute to climate change mitigation.

Sustainable forest management (SFM) can contribute to the reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions to the atmosphere. First, SFM can enhance the capacity of forest ecosystem to uptake CO₂ from the atmosphere and to store carbon in biomass and soil [2]. Then after harvesting carbon is shifted to long-lived wood products, which delays carbon release into the atmosphere, and in fuel wood to produce energy as a substitute for fossil fuels and energy-intensive materials.

Even though fuel wood has generally been considered to be carbon neutral, the carbon stored in the biomass is immediately released in atmosphere. At the contrary, wood products can store carbon for decades or even centuries, and consequently it is crucial to produce wood of good quality.

In this context, our objective was to evaluate different silvicultural options in producing round wood and fuel wood.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Study sites

The study was performed in a transect of three Italian mountain beech forests (Fig. 1).

The northern study site of the transect is located in the Cansiglio (Veneto Region). The forest consists of an even-aged (120 to 145 years) stand, where low-mixed thinning is repeated every 20-25 years on the same management unit. The long-lasting repetition of silvicultural practices resulted in a fairly uniform stand structure [3].

The Chiarano-Sparvera site is located in Central Italy, in the Apennine mountains (Abruzzo Region). The stand is an even-aged high forest arising from a conversion treatment [3].

The Mongiana study site is located in the Southern Apennine (Calabria Region). The stand is even-aged (about 70 years) with trees from the former cycles are still present. The random occurrence of trees much older than the dominant tree age makes the physiognomy less regular than a typical even-aged beech forest [3].

Figure 1: Location of the three study sites and the survey protocol applied in Cansiglio (a), Chiarano (b) and Mongiana (c).

In each beech forest, a trial was performed in a area of 30 hectares. Different silvicultural treatments (theses) were identified and randomly assigned in three replicates to each compartment. Each sector was defined using a 3-ha grid. In each sector, a cluster of three circular sampling plots was established within each compartment, according to a systematic design [3].

2.2 Woody biomass and assortments assessment

In each circular plot, diameter at breast height (DBH) were measured to evaluate the biomass removed by each silvicultural treatments (theses). Using assortments tables, which give the different woody assortment for each diameter, we assessed the amount of round wood and fuel wood [4].

2.3 Data analysis

Biomass and assortments data were tested using two Way Analysis of Variance, with site and treatment as

factor, followed by post-hoc test (Holm-Sidak method).

Communality analysis (CA) was applied to a multiple linear regression to disentangle the effects of each independent variable [5].

3 RESULTS

3.1 Effect of silvicultural treatments on stand biomass

In fig. 2, the above ground woody biomass (stem and branches) before and after the silvicultural treatment are reported.

A significant difference was found among the above ground woody biomass of the sites ($F=5.603$, $P\text{-value}=0.015$), with Chiarano –Sparvera ($248.48 \pm 5.6 \text{ Mg dw ha}^{-1}$) showing a lower value than Cansiglio ($288.48 \pm 4.03 \text{ Mg dw ha}^{-1}$) and Mongiana ($291.48 \pm 8.00 \text{ Mg dw ha}^{-1}$). Only in Mongiana, significant differences between the plot assigned to the two different thesis ($t=4.691$, $P\text{-value}<0.001$) were found. The percentage of biomass removed by the two silvicultural thesis was different only in Cansiglio ($t=2.393$, $P\text{-value}=0.04$). However, after the different silvicultural treatments, only in Mongiana was found a difference among the plots with the two different thesis ($t=2.759$, $P\text{-value}=0.01$).

Figure 2: Amounts of above ground woody biomass before (grey) and after (red) the silvicultural treatment for each innovative (_Inn) and traditional (_Trad) treatment in each site. Bar represent standard error.

3.2 Effect of silvicultural treatment on woody assortment

The amount of round wood, the highest assortment, was affected both site ($F=20.210$, $P\text{-value}<0.001$) and treatment ($F=20.210$, $P\text{-value}<0.001$). In all the sites innovative treatments produced an higher amount of round wood than traditional ones. Even the fuel wood amount was affected by site ($F=81.506$, $P\text{-value}<0.001$) and treatment ($F=16.850$, $P\text{-value}<0.001$) (Fig.3).

In general the amount of round wood (RW) is dependent by the biomass before the treatment (x_1) and the percentage of biomass removed (x_2) ($RW = -76.167 + (0.302x_1) + (132.403x_2)$, $R^2=0.732$, $P\text{-value}<0.01$), with the percentage of biomass removed affecting the 67% of the whole variability.

Figure 3: Amounts of round (blue) and fuel wood (green) produced for each innovative (_Inn) and traditional (_Trad) treatment in each site. Bar represent standard error.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Different silvicultural treatments impact the production of different assortment. In all the study sites, the innovative thesis produced higher amount of both round and fuel wood. This can be related to a higher percentage of biomass removed as in Cansiglio. However, the harvested amount of wood is not far from the one extracted by traditional thinning, but they can differ for the dimension of harvested trees.

This derives from the innovative thesis approach which consisted of the identification of a non-fixed number of scattered, well-shaped trees (usually in the predominant-dominant social classes) and crown thinning of neighbouring competitors to promote better growth ability of selected trees.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Nabuurs, G.; Verkerk, P. J.; Schelhaas, M.; Ramón, J.; Olabarria, G.; Trasobares, A.; Cienciala, E. Climate- Smart Forestry : mitigation impacts in three European regions; Hetemäki, L., Ed.; From Scien.; European Forest Institute, 2018; ISBN 978-952-5980-54-7.
- [2] D'Andrea, E.; Micali, M.; Sicuriello, F.; Cammarano, M.; Ferlan, M.; Skudnik, M.; Mali, B.; Čater, M.; Simončič, P.; De Cinti, B.; Matteucci, G.; Levanic, T.; Marinsek, A.; Kobal, M. Improving carbon sequestration and stocking as a function of forestry. Ital. J. Agron. 2016, 11, 56–60.
- [3] Di Salvatore, U.; Tonti, D.; Bascietto, M.; Chiavetta, U.; Cantiani, P.; Fabbio, G.; Becagli, C.; Bertini, G.; Sansone, D.; Skudnik, M.; Kobal, M.; Kutnar, L.; Ferreira, A.; Kobler, A.; Kovač, M.; Ferretti, F. ManFor C.Bd sites and the drivers of forest functions. Ital. J. Agron. 2016, 11, 64–95..
- [4] Castellani, C. TAVOLE STEREOMETRICHE ED ALSOMETRICHE COSTRUITE PER BOSCHI ITALIANI; Istituto Sperimentale per

l'Assestamento Forestale e per l'Alpicoltura: Villazzano (TN), 1980.

- [5] Huang, R.; Zhu, H.; Liu, X.; Liang, E.; Griebinger, J.; Wu, G.; Li, X.; Bräuning, A. Does increasing intrinsic water use efficiency (iWUE) stimulate tree growth at natural alpine timberline on the southeastern Tibetan Plateau? *Glob. Planet. Change* 2017, 148, 217–226, doi:10.1016/j.gloplacha.2016.11.017.

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

- The Authors are grateful to the MANFOR C.BD. staff for their helpful cooperation

